

LANGUAGE AND CULTURE IN ENGLISH CLASSROOMS

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Abstract: The way in which students in different cultures greet each other and express politeness is highlighted in this article. Communication patterns have also been analysed with regard to Japan and the English language.

Key words: Culture, greetings, Japanese language, English language politeness, forms of address, linguistic tool.

Understanding our artistic values, beliefs, and comprehensive from a distance is a prerequisite for effective communication, and it is embodied in the capacity for cultural awareness. Cultural mindfulness is essential when interacting with members of different societies. It explains why we act in certain ways, how we perceive the world and why we respond in certain ways. There are differences in how people perceive, understand, and quantify effects. Misconceptions occur when I use my meanings to try and make sense of your reality. What is deemed appropriate in one culture is perpetually unhappy in another. It is almost a reflex for an Italian to view Americans as perpetual workers, businessmen who discuss deals over lunch, and who prefer to sip their coffee while running down the street rather than in a bar. It does not mean Americans are hyperactive and Italians are lazy; rather it indicates that people's interpretations of certain social norms, such as eating lunch or regale, can vary depending on the society in question. Lunch, regale, or even just stopping for coffee has a social connotation in Italy, where people value relationships above all else. People gather to chat, unwind, and get to know one another better. Lunches can be a part of closing a deal with in the USA, where time is plutocrat and people bandy the issues and subscribe a contract over coffee.

The primary cause of misconstructions is when we fail to be mindful of our own behavioral norms and apply them to other people. Lacking more information, we often assume something instead of figuring out the meaning of a gesture for the individual making it. G. in Japan, it is considered Impolite to stare directly into your face. As culture is unconscious to us, it is a delicate task to become aware of our artistic dynamics. From birth, we have acquired the ability to perceive and act upon effects in an unconscious manner. Because of our gests, values, and artistic upbringing, we see and act in certain ways. Sometimes we have to go beyond our creative comfort zones to understand how much culture influences our gesture. To gain more insight into our

artistic qualities, it is incredibly beneficial to get input on our gesture from international colleagues. Misunderstandings may also result from projected parallels. We run the risk of missing the possibility that someone is not like us when we assume they are. If we draw parallels where none exist, we could, nevertheless, act incorrectly. Prior to evidence of similarity, it is safer to assume differences. Pronominal systems in Greek are similar to those in many other European languages, such as French tu/vous, Russian ty/vy, German Du/Sie, and Greek esi/esis. Social distance or status differences between the interactants in the hassle determine the form of the alternate person plural pronoun, which is generally addressed to one Hearer as a means of indicating formality and or politeness. The pronoun V itself does not need to appear in the judgment because, in Greek, the verb’s inflectional system indicates person and number and spares certain pronouns. This is another point to note. In the summary, the polite plural in Greek formalism serves as a vehicle for expressing both social distance and politeness. Polite plurals are restricted to the use of an alternative plural verb for a single addressee and can only be used in direct [3]. The outcome of the meeting depends on the speaker’s appropriate use of verb tenses and pronouns when speaking to the listener. A communication breakdown or the expression of specific ideas and emotions from the Speaker toward the Listener and/or their relationship may result from the Avoidance of this Verbal Tool in further anticipated situations. Greek has a number of address options in addition to the T/V pronominal system, which are listed below. Title T kirie, kiria, eispinis

- First Name(FN)
- Title Name(TFN)
- Surname(LN)
- Title Surname(TLN)
- Title Position Title
- Multiple Naming(MN)
- Naming(NN)

KIRIOS SPINIS KIRIA

The form of TFN, which is not available in English, serves as a transitional option in Greek that helps close the gap between formality and closeness. Additionally, it is probably the most common construction in regular meetings[4]. The address’s format influences the number that is selected. The alternate singular is always used after the listener’s FN, and the plural is used after T and T LN. It is possible for the construction T FN to be singular or plural. Apart from the typical titles, Mr. kirios, Mrs. Kiria and Miss spinis are a few examples of words that can be used as formal, impersonal forms of address. Among these forms are positions or professions PT.

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